

RESEARCH ARTICLE

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Theoretical structural study of van der Waals complexes between oxazole and atmospheric gases CO₂ and N₂ for capture applications.

[version 3; peer review: 2 approved, 1 approved with reservations]

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V3 First published: 08 Jan 2025, 5:3
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.18925.1>
Second version: 29 Jul 2025, 5:3
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.18925.2>
Latest published: 11 Sep 2025, 5:3
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.18925.3>

Abstract

Background

The objective of this study is to explore the potential of oxazole (C₃H₃NO), a fascinating heterocyclic compound naturally present, which is a potential ligand in the construction of Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs) for the selective capture of CO₂ in a nitrogen-rich atmosphere, using both molecular and solid-state simulation techniques.

Methods

This study investigates the equilibrium structures and binding energies of van der Waals aggregates formed by an oxazole molecule with nonpolar molecules such as CO₂ and N₂, considering both two-body systems (oxazole-CO₂ and oxazole-N₂) and three-body systems (oxazole-CO₂-N₂ and oxazole-CO₂/N₂-Au₆/Cu₆/Zn₃O₃). Molecular computations for these systems are conducted using ab initio calculations at the MP2/aug-cc-pVXZ level of theory, where X = (D, T).

Open Peer Review

Approval Status

	1	2	3
version 3 (revision) 11 Sep 2025			
version 2 (revision) 29 Jul 2025	 view	 view	 view
version 1 08 Jan 2025	 view		

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Additionally, solid-state simulations analyze the adsorption behaviors and energies of oxazole-CO₂ and oxazole-N₂ on metallic surfaces: Au, Cu and ZnO(111) through Monte Carlo methods.

Results

We find that the oxazole exhibits more adsorption selectivity for CO₂ than for N₂. Adding a second gas to the most stable complexes, oxazole@CO₂ and oxazole@N₂, the oxazole capture ability does not vary. On the contrary, it strengthens the adsorption energy of three-body complexes compared to two-body complexes. The addition of metallic clusters (Au₆, Cu₆, Zn₃O₃) and metallic surfaces (Au, Cu, ZnO) enhances the adsorption capacity, where Cu₆ is particularly efficient. Both ZnO and Cu surfaces offer significant adsorption advantages while remaining economically feasible.

Conclusions

This study demonstrates that oxazole exhibits a strong selectivity for CO₂ over N₂, with the addition of metallic clusters and surfaces significantly enhancing its adsorption capacity. These findings highlight the potential of oxazole-based materials for effective gas capture and separation, with positive implications for environmental sustainability.

Plain language summary

This research project focuses on gas capture and separation, especially for molecules like carbon dioxide (CO₂) and nitrogen (N₂), which are crucial in both industrial and environmental contexts. Metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) show promise for efficient CO₂ capture due to their adjustable structures and large surface areas. However, the use of oxazole, a specific molecule, for CO₂ capture in these structures has been little explored. This study examines how oxazole interacts with CO₂ and N₂ molecules, forming aggregates bound by van der Waals forces (a type of molecular attraction). Results show that oxazole favors binding with CO₂ over nitrogen, making it potentially useful for gas separation. By adding metallic clusters, such as gold, copper, or zinc oxide, the adsorption capacity of oxazole further improves, especially with copper, while remaining affordable.

This study highlights oxazole's potential for effective gas capture, contributing to more sustainable and environmentally friendly technologies.

Keywords

Adsorption, CO₂ capture, N₂, atmosphere, ab initio, MOF's.

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Competing interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Grant information: This project has received funding from the [European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme][European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme] under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No [872081] (ATMOS).

The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

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How to cite this article: Belasri A, Tahiri F, Douass O *et al.* **Theoretical structural study of van der Waals complexes between oxazole and atmospheric gases CO₂ and N₂ for capture applications. [version 3; peer review: 2 approved, 1 approved with reservations]** Open Research Europe 2025, 5:3 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.18925.3>

First published: 08 Jan 2025, 5:3 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.18925.1>

REVISED Amendments from Version 2

In this revised version, we have addressed all reviewer comments by improving clarity, consistency, and scientific accuracy. Major corrections include the consistent use of "CO₂-Oxa" and "N₂-Oxa" throughout the text and figures, rephrasing of sentences for better readability, addition of computational details including CCSD(T)-F12b single-point validations, revisions of Figure 1, Figure 4, Figure 5, and Figure 6 with updated labels and annotations, inclusion of Eint(CCSD(T)-F12) values in Table 5 to improve the validation of MP2/AVTZ results, and updates to the reference numbering following the inclusion of new citations.

Any further responses from the reviewers can be found at the end of the article

Introduction

The exploration of carbon dioxide capture and separation from gas mixtures by adsorption based on porous materials searching for low-cost and high efficiency, has been a focal point in research¹⁻⁷, aiming to address environmental concerns and enhance industrial processes^{5,6}. Gas adsorption and separation, particularly involving quadrupolar species such as carbon dioxide (CO₂) and nitrogen (N₂), have gained considerable interest due to their importance in industrial and environmental contexts. Metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) are porous crystalline materials formed by organic structures that act as ligands⁸ connected by metal ions or clusters^{9,10}. They have been considered to be efficient for CO₂ capture tools owing to their adjustable and tunable structures², extensive surfaces^{11,12}, large surface areas^{13,14}, customizable functionalities^{15,16}, and high mechanical and thermal stabilities¹⁷. Specific organic ligands, such as heterocycles like carboxylic acids^{18,19}, amines²⁰, imidazoles²¹⁻²⁵, triazoles²⁶, pyridines²⁷, benzenes²⁸, naphthalenes²⁹, benzimidazoles³⁰, etc., enable the regulation of (MOFs) properties, thereby enhancing their capability for selective adsorption and thermal stability³¹, making them particularly suitable for gas adsorption and separation processes³². (MOFs) based on imidazole have gained interest due to the ability to design various types of architectures such as rigid, flexible, interpenetrating, etc., to influence the size of cavity pores and different types of supramolecular interactions within the pore^{33,34}.

In our previous study²¹⁻²⁴, we highlighted the significant ability of imidazole to form van der Waals complexes with several greenhouse gases, including CO₂, CH₄, and SF₆, as well as with pollutants such as SO₂ and NH₃ and gas such as CO. This interaction is particularly relevant for selectively capturing CO₂ from mixtures containing these gases. Although oxazole (C₃H₃NO) is a fascinating heterocyclic compound naturally present³⁵, its capacity as a ligand in the construction of CO₂ capturing (MOFs) has not been thoroughly investigated. This provides an opportunity for further research aimed to valorize the properties of oxazole in developing efficient (MOFs) for CO₂ capture, contributing to advancements in environmental sustainability and gas separation technologies. Our goal is the theoretical characterization of van der Waals aggregates formed with one oxazole molecule and nonpolar molecules such as carbon dioxide (CO₂) and nitrogen (N₂). CO₂ is known to have significant environmental impacts on global weather

patterns and human life³⁶. Anthropogenic emissions of N₂ can indirectly lead to an increase in NO_x levels in the atmosphere. When N₂ reacts with atmospheric oxygen, it converts into nitrogen oxides (NO_x) such as NO and NO₂. These NO_x compounds have consequences on air quality, human health, and the environment, contributing to smog formation, acid rain, and causing harmful effects on respiratory systems and lung tissues³⁷.

In this work, we perform a systematic evaluation of ligands containing both nitrogen and oxygen for their interaction energies with CO₂ and N₂ by using both molecular and solid-state simulation techniques. In the first approach, we use the possible accurate ab initio methods to calculate the binding energies (BEs) of the two body systems (CO₂-Oxazole-BEs & N₂-Oxazole-BEs). The analysis of the ternary systems (CO₂-oxazole-N₂-BEs) and (oxazole-CO₂/N₂-Au₆/Cu₆/Zn₃O₃) using the same method was conducted to understand the interactions among CO₂, oxazole, and N₂ within these systems, to examine their influence on CO₂ separation and capture strategies in gas mixtures, and predict the capacity of new materials to selectively capture and store CO₂ over N₂ in N₂-rich atmospheres. Indeed, the presence of N₂ can significantly influence CO₂ capture performance in (MOFs), taking into account their common presence in atmospheric and industrial environments, emphasizing the crucial role of computational methods in designing nanomaterials for carbon capture technologies.

On the other hand, the Monte Carlo solid-state simulations were employed to investigate the interactions between oxazole and the (111) surfaces of Au, Cu, and ZnO. These materials were selected for their unique electronic properties and practical relevance. Gold (Au) is frequently used as a reference due to its stability and well-characterized surface chemistry³⁸, Copper (Cu) is chosen for its economic viability and its proven effectiveness in enhancing adsorption processes³⁹. While zinc oxide ZnO was included in this study for its unique semiconducting, piezoelectric, and photoelectric properties and high surface area⁴⁰.

Computational details

All the electronic computations were performed using the Gaussian 09 Revision C.01⁴¹ and MOLPRO⁴², as well as the Material Studio (BIOVIA, 2020) program⁴³. An appropriate free alternative software for this purpose is GAMESS (US), a powerful tool for electronic structure calculations that supports HF, DFT, MP2, and other methods, and ORCA, a versatile quantum chemistry program renowned for its computational efficiency and support for DFT, HF, and post-HF techniques.

We have combined the most accurate possible ab initio method, and Monte Carlo solid-state simulations⁴⁴, to investigate the interaction between CO₂ and N₂ and oxazole (Oxa), either isolated, attached to gold, copper and ZnO cluster or surface.

The study employed the second-order Møller–Plesset theory (MP2)^{45,46} within the Gaussian software to compute the equilibrium structures and spectroscopic properties of both

isolated species and complexes included two-body systems like oxazole-CO₂ and oxazole-N₂. Additionally, the three-body systems such as oxazole-CO₂-N₂ and oxazole-CO₂/N₂-Au₆/Cu₆/Zn₃O₃ were investigated. For an accurate depiction of small systems, in these computations, the atoms were described using Dunning and co-workers' aug-cc-pVXZ basis set (abbreviated as AVXZ, where X=D, T)⁴⁷, augmented with diffuse atomic orbitals to capture long-range interactions. Specifically, AVTZ was employed for oxazole-CO₂ and oxazole-N₂, while AVDZ was used for oxazole-CO₂-N₂ and oxazole-CO₂/N₂- cluster complexes.

Monte Carlo (MC) simulation⁴⁸ is a widely used computational method for investigating molecular adsorption on surfaces, particularly for estimating adsorption energies (E_{ads}) and modeling adsorption isotherms. Based on the Metropolis algorithm⁴⁹, it explores configurational space by evaluating randomly generated molecular states according to energy changes and thermodynamic probability. In this study, the Adsorption Locator module, implemented in Materials Studio 2020 (BIOVIA)⁴³, was employed in conjunction with the COMPASS II force field⁵⁰ to examine the adsorption energies of oxazole-N₂ and oxazole-CO₂ on gold, copper, and zinc oxide surfaces. Atomistic grand canonical Monte Carlo (GCMC) simulations were performed to estimate the adsorption isotherms of oxazole-CO₂ and oxazole-N₂ on Au (111), Cu (111), and ZnO (111) surface.

As a free alternative to Material Studio, I recommend the open-source software packages Quantum ESPRESSO and CP2K. The first program, Quantum ESPRESSO, is a comprehensive suite for quantum simulations, ideal for materials modeling and the simulation of solids, liquids, and nanostructures.

<https://www.quantum-espresso.org/>

The second program, CP2K, is also free and open-source software, widely used for molecular dynamics simulations and quantum chemistry calculations, particularly for systems with large numbers of atoms.

<https://www.cp2k.org/>

The Au, Cu, and ZnO crystal structures have been imported from the Materials Studio database. Surfaces were built by clicking 'Build', then 'Surface', and then 'Cleave Surface'. In the following menu, the cleaving plane (1 1 1) was chosen, and then afterward, the 'Symmetry' option was used to construct a supercell. All the surface structures were prepared with three layers, as illustrated in Figure 5.

The structures of oxazole, oxazole-N₂, and oxazole-CO₂ were optimized to obtain their lowest-energy configurations using the COMPASS II force field, as implemented in the Forcite Module. This same force field was used in the Monte Carlo simulations. The simulations were done utilizing the Adsorption Locator Module in the Materials Studio 2020 package from BIOVIA. These simulations involved 10 cycles of 10,000 steps each, providing insights into adsorption processes relevant to catalysis, materials science, and environmental applications.

Therefore, a detailed investigation of adsorption behaviors and energies of the fixed molecules on the chosen surfaces provides valuable insight into their eventual interactions and stability.

The minimum character of all the optimized structures is evidenced by the presence of all positive harmonic frequencies, indicating that the system is at its energy minimum, reflecting a stable and optimized configuration. The binding energy (BE) between oxazole and CO₂ or N₂ was initially evaluated for optimized geometries using Second-order Møller-Plesset perturbation theory (MP2) in connection with aug-cc-pVTZ basis set (denoted in this paper by AVTZ). To confirm the accuracy of MP2, single-point energy calculations were subsequently performed on the MP2 geometries using the explicitly correlated coupled cluster method, CCSD(T)-F12b^{51,52}, as implemented in MOLPRO⁴², in combination with the AVTZ orbital basis set. The default auxiliary basis sets AVnZ/MP2FIT and VnZ/JKFIT were employed for density fitting (DF) and resolution of the identity (RI), respectively. The binding energies (BEs) were calculated using the following energy expression:

$$BE = E_{\text{Complex}} - (E_{\text{oxazole}} + E_{\text{gaz}})$$

where: BE is the binding energy, E_{complex} is the total energy of the oxazole-gas complex, E_{Oxazole} is the total energy of the isolated oxazole molecule, and E_{gaz} is the total energy of the isolated gas molecule (CO₂ or N₂). For a more accurate estimation of the interaction energy, the basis set superposition error (BSSE) was corrected using the Boys and Bernardi method⁵³. Additionally, the zero-point vibrational energy correction (ZPVE) was also taken into account for all geometries⁵⁴.

For the complexes between oxazole and CO₂ or N₂ - cluster (Au₆, Cu₆ or Zn₃O₃) we employed the MP2 method with aug-cc-pVDZ for non-metals and LANL2DZ ECP⁵⁵ for metals, and for the adsorption of CO₂ and N₂ on Au, Cu, and ZnO (111) surfaces, we used the Monte Carlo computational technique.

The binding energies (BEs) were calculated using the following energy expression:

$$BE = E_{\text{Complex}} - (E_{\text{Oxa-CO2/N2}} + E_{\text{Cluster/Surface}})$$

where: BE is the binding energy E_{complex} , is the total energy of the Oxa CO₂/N₂- cluster (cluster = Au₆/Cu₆ or Zn₃O₃) or Surface Au, Cu or ZnO (111) complexes, $E_{\text{Oxa-CO2/N2}}$ is the total energy of the complex Oxazole+CO₂ or Oxazole+N₂, and $E_{\text{Cluster/Surface}}$ is the total energy of the isolated gas cluster (Au₆, Cu₆ or Zn₃O₃) or Surface Au(111), Cu (111) or ZnO (111). For a more accurate estimation of the interaction energy of Oxazole CO₂/N₂- cluster (cluster= Au₆/Cu₆ or Zn₃O₃) the zero-point vibrational energy correction (ZPVE) was also taken into account for all geometries.

Results and discussions

Equilibrium structure of the complexes

To examine the molecular-level adsorption of CO₂ and N₂ on oxazole, we first located the CO₂ and N₂ molecules at the N1

site of oxazole (refer to Figure 1) and then we oriented them around it to explore all possible equilibrium structures. It's worth noting that the number of stable structures increases the likelihood of gas capture. Despite multiple attempts, the optimization results at the MP2/AVTZ level consistently converged toward one of the structures presented in Figure 1A and 1B, which characterize the complexes formed by oxazole with CO₂ and N₂.

The study carried out at the MP2/AVTZ level on the Oxazole-CO₂ complex reveals the existence of two stable structures labeled I1 and I2 (cf. Figure 2A, Table 1). In structure I1 ($E_r = 0.0$ kcal/mol), identified as the global minimum, the bond is established through an interaction between the electron donor-acceptor (EDA) sites of CO₂ and oxazole (RO10-H6 = 2.6956 Å and RC9-N1 = 2.8418 Å). However, in structure I2 ($E_r = 1.31$ kcal/mol), the bond is maintained through a

Figure 1. The atom labeling of the complex Oxazole + CO₂ (A), Oxazole + N₂ (B) and Oxazole and the five principal complexation pathways, I1, I2, I3, I4, and I5 (C).

Figure 2. The equilibrium geometries and the MP2/AVTZ relative energies of the oxazole + CO₂ (A) and oxazole + N₂ (B) Van der Waals complexes.

donor-acceptor electron exchange (EDA), where the oxygen atom of CO₂ interacts with H8 of oxazole (RO10H8 = 2.7362 Å) and the carbon atom of CO₂ interacts with the oxygen of oxazole (RC9-O4 = 2.8340 Å).

Additionally, the study of the complex between N₂ and oxazole, still at the MP2/AVTZ level, revealed the existence of four adsorption sites as outlined in Figure 2B and Table 3. These sites are labeled as follows: I1A (E_r = 0.0 kcal/mol), I1B (E_r = 0.01 kcal/mol), I2A (E_r = 0.28 kcal/mol), and I5 (E_r = 0.57 kcal/mol). These distinct structures depict various stable configurations of the N₂-oxazole complex. Predominantly, the

key interactions observed in the stable structures occur where hydrogen bonds link N₂ to oxazole. Additionally, the equilibrium distances within the van der Waals systems RN9H_x (X=6,7,8) exhibit the following variations: RN9H6 = 2.7302 Å for I1A, RN9H7 = 2.7437 Å for I1B, RN9H6 = 2.7529 Å for I2A, and RN9H8 = 2.5885 Å for I5.

Table 1 and Table 3 present the structural parameters at the MP2/AVTZ level, while Table 2 and Table 4 provide the MP2/AVTZ harmonic frequencies for each examined complex. The parameters of the van der Waals aggregates are compared to those of the corresponding isolated components.

Table 1. Total electronic energies (E, in a.u.), relative energies (E_r, in kcal/mol) and structural parameters (Distances in Å; angles in degrees) of the two equilibrium structures of the Oxazole-CO₂ complexes calculated with MP2/aug-cc-pVTZ.

Oxazole (C1)		I1 (C1)		I2 (C1)	
		ROH	2.6956	ROH	2.7362
		RCN	2.8418	RCO	2.8340
E	-245.639836	E	-433.968056	E	-433.965972
		E _r	0.0	E _r	1.31
C2N1	1.2996	C2N1	1.3011	C2N1	1.2987
C3N1	1.3862	C3N1	1.3858	C3N1	1.3869
O4C2	1.3552	O4C2	1.3531	O4C2	1.3570
C5C3	1.3596	C5C3	1.3597	C5C3	1.3593
H6C2	1.0755	H6C2	1.0757	H6C2	1.0757
H7C3	1.0752	H7C3	1.0752	H7C3	1.0752
H8C5	1.0739	H8N4	1.0739	H8N4	1.0741
C3N1C2	104.0	C3N1C2	104.2	C3N1C2	104.1
O4C2N1	114.7	O4C2N1	114.5	O4C2N1	114.6
C5C3N1	109.1	C5C3N1	109.0	C5C3N1	109.3
H6C2N1	128.6	H6C2N1	128.2	H6C2N1	128.8
H7C3N1	122.1	H7C3N1	122.1	H7C3N1	122.0
H8C5O4	116.7	H8C5O4	116.8	H8C5O4	116.6
CO₂					
E	-188.321641				
CO	1.1702	O10C9	1.1718	O10C9	1.1709
		O11C9	1.1686	O11C9	1.1690
<OCO	180.0	<OCO	177.6	<OCO	179.3
		O10H6	2.6956	O10H8	2.7362
		O10H6C2	104.2	O10H8C5	111.2
		C9O10H6	114.7	C9O10H8	113.6
		C9N1	2.8418	C9O4	2.8340
		C9N1C2	106.8	C9O4C2	142.8
		O10C9N1	86.1	O10C9O4	85.8

Table 2. Harmonic fundamental frequencies (ω , in cm^{-1}) of CO_2 , oxazole, and the two equilibrium geometries of the oxazole- CO_2 complexes calculated at the MP2/AVTZ level of theory.

	Ω							
	Oxazole		CO_2		I1		I2	
ω_1	a	3330			a	3331	a	3330
ω_2		3311				3312		3309
ω_3		3299				3300		3299
ω_4			σ_u	2402		2402		2404
ω_5		1546				1546		1547
ω_6		1508				1506		1507
ω_7		1355				1355		1354
ω_8			σ_g	1326		1327		1328
ω_9		1272				1269		1270
ω_{10}		1185				1189		1182
ω_{11}		1141				1144		1138
ω_{12}		1109				1111		1108
ω_{13}		1086				1086		1082
ω_{14}		915				917		917
ω_{15}		905				909		904
ω_{16}		864				865		868
ω_{17}		827				836		827
ω_{18}		763				766		771
ω_{19}		665				667		664
ω_{20}			π	659		662		660
ω_{21}			π	659		637		651
ω_{22}		628				628		626
ω_{23}						132		100
ω_{24}						88		80
ω_{25}						52		39
ω_{26}						44		38
ω_{27}						29		21

During the formation of weak intramolecular bonds, the structure of the oxazole ring and N_2 undergoes minimal changes (see Table 1 and Table 3). However, a significant deformation is observed in the CO_2 molecule, resulting in the loss of its symmetry. This deformation is particularly pronounced in the oxazole- CO_2 complexes I1 and I2 (see Table 1), where the C-O bond in CO_2 tends to shorten (O11C9: 1.1686 Å for I1, 1.1690 Å for I2), while the distance O10C9 is elongated (1.1718 Å for I1, 1.1709 Å for I2), compared to free

CO_2 (CO=1.1702 Å). Additionally, the $\angle\text{OCO}$ angle is bent away from the linear configuration of a free CO_2 molecule, measuring 177.6 degrees for I1 and 179.3 degrees for I2, respectively. This deformation is attributed to the formation of the van der Waals complexes between CO_2 and oxazole, leading to electron redistribution and strengthening of the C-O bond.

Harmonic frequencies were computed to ensure minimal energy for all structures. Notably, in Table 2 and Table 4, certain low frequencies (5 frequencies for Oxazole- CO_2 , ω_{23} - ω_{27} , and for Oxazole- N_2 , ω_{20} - ω_{24}) emerge, which were not observed for the monomers. This situation allows for the use of a Born-Oppenheimer-type approach, which distinguishes between intramolecular and intermolecular vibrations. Intermolecular vibrations more closely resemble hindered rotations or tunneling motions. Generally, there is a strong coupling between different intermolecular degrees of freedom. The deformation vibrations of O-C-O in complexes I1 and I2 occur at frequencies of 637 cm^{-1} and 651 cm^{-1} , respectively. These modes experience significant frequency shifts compared to the CO_2 monomer, approximately 8 cm^{-1} for complex I2 and 22 cm^{-1} for complex I1. Furthermore, the symmetric and antisymmetric intermolecular O-C stretching modes with frequencies $\omega_8 = 1328 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\omega_4 = 2402 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for complex I2 have shifted by 2 cm^{-1} from frequencies of $\omega_8 = 1326 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\omega_4 = 2404 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for the CO_2 monomer. In the oxazole- N_2 complex, the stretching mode of N-N is not influenced by the formation of the hydrogen bond between the N of N_2 and the H of oxazole. Thus, the intermolecular stretching vibrations H..N-N(ω_{21}) in the optimal structure are observed at frequencies of 63 cm^{-1} , 58 cm^{-1} , 54 cm^{-1} , and 57 cm^{-1} for I1A, I1B, I2A, and I5, respectively.

Binding energies

Two body complexes type oxazole- CO_2 and oxazole- N_2

The binding energy is crucial for understanding, predicting, and enhancing the performance of adsorbent materials in greenhouse gas and pollutant capture processes. It determines the interaction between the host and the guest, as well as the properties of the adsorbent material. A more negative adsorption energy generally indicates a stronger adsorption interaction. For this reason, the binding energies of all previously mentioned stable forms, are computed via the MP2/AVTZ approach and including the zero-point vibrational energy (ZPVE) along with as well as the Boys and Bernardi correction (BSSE), are listed in Table 5. Our calculations indicate that oxazole is energetically favored as an adsorbent for both our adsorbates although CO_2 shows a higher capacity to bind oxazole rings. The range of CO_2 binding energies spans from -4.13 to -2.82 kcal/mol, while for N_2 , the energies range from -1.77 to -1.19 kcal/mol. Based on the adsorption energies, the nitrogen site of the oxazole is the most stable site for CO_2 adsorption, and Hydrogen 6 is the most stable site for N_2 adsorption. The zero-point vibrational energy (ZPVE) correction ranges from 0.39 to 0.51 kcal/mol for the CO_2 complexes and from 0.32 to 0.39 kcal/mol for the N_2 complexes. On the other hand, the BSSE correction is between 0.02 and 0.09 kcal/mol for CO_2 and 0.05 kcal/mol for N_2 .

Table 3. Total electronic energies (E, in a.u.), relative energies (E_r , in kcal/mol) and structural parameters (Distances in Å; angles in degrees) of the four equilibrium structures of the Oxazole-N₂ complex calculated with MP2/aug-cc-pVTZ.

Oxazole (C1)		I1A (C1)		I1B (C1)		I2A (C1)		I5 (C1)	
		R _{NH}	2.7302	R _{NH}	2.7437	R _{NH}	2.7529	R _{NH}	2.5885
E	-245.639836	E	-355.007379	E	-355.007363	E	-355.006923	E	-355.006474
		E_r	0.0	E_r	0.01	E_r	0.28	E_r	0.57
C2N1	2.9962	C2N1	1.3003	C2N1	1.30006	C2N1	1.2997	C2N1	1.2998
C3N1	1.38622	C3N1	1.3860	C3N1	1.3867	C3N1	1.3859	C3N1	1.3863
O4C2	1.35519	O4C2	1.3549	O4C2	1.3547	O4C2	1.3565	O4C2	1.3550
C5C3	1.35957	C5C3	1.3597	C5C3	1.3597	C5C3	1.3597	C5C3	1.3599
H6C2	1.07554	H6C2	1.0754	H6C2	1.0756	H6C2	1.0752	H6C2	1.0755
H7C3	1.07521	H7C3	1.0752	H7C3	1.0751	H7C3	1.0752	H7C3	1.0752
H8C5	1.07390	H8C5	1.0739	H8C5	1.07388	H8C5	1.0733	H8C5	1.0738
C3N1C2	103.99	C3N1C2	104.0	C3N1C2	104.0	C3N1C2	104.0	C3N1C2	104.0
O4C2N1	114.70	O4C2N1	114.7	O4C2N1	114.7	O4C2N1	114.6	O4C2N1	114.7
C5C3N1	109.13	C5C3N1	109.1	C5C3N1	109.1	C5C3N1	109.1	C5C3N1	109.2
H6C2N1	128.59	H6C2N1	128.4	H6C2N1	128.6	H6C2N1	128.8	H6C2N1	128.7
H7C3N1	122.09	H7C3N1	122.1	H7C3N1	122.0	H7C3N1	122.1	H7C3N1	122.0
H8C5O4	116.75	H8C5O4	116.9	H8C5O4	116.8	H8C5O4	116.8	H8C5O4	116.7
N₂									
E	-109.364800								
NN	1.11401	NN	1.11387	NN	1.11408	NN	1.11396	NN	1.11401
		N9H6	2.7302	N9H7	2.7437	N9H6	2.7529	N9H8	2.5885
		N9H6C2	109.2	N9H7C3	113.3	N9H6C2	114.9	N9H8C5	167.7
		N10N9H6	147.3	N10N9H7	144.1	N10N9H6	114.9	N10N9H8	172.1

Single-point CCSD(T)-F12/AVTZ-F12 calculations were also performed to provide accurate reference values for the interaction energies of the oxazole-CO₂ and oxazole-N₂ complexes. In comparison, the MP2/AVTZ method predicts interaction energies close to these reference values, with deviations of approximately - 0.18 kcal/mol for oxazole-CO₂ and ranging from - 0.41 to - 0.58 kcal/mol for oxazole-N₂.

Three body complexes type CO₂-Oxazole-N₂

Since this article focuses on the CO₂ separation properties relative to N₂, the most abundant gas in Earth's atmosphere (78.084%)⁵⁶, our aim is to understand, at the molecular level, whether oxazole-based (MOFs) can simultaneously capture two different gases and how the CO₂ capture capacity varies in the presence of N₂, which a third body can alter the interaction between two bodies. To achieve this, we performed geometry optimizations on three-body systems, namely N₂-oxazole-CO₂, starting from various configurations where CO₂ and N₂

occupy the equilibrium positions of the two-body systems, oxazole-CO₂ and oxazole-N₂. We then examined the capture of the second gas. The resulting structures are presented in Table 6 and illustrated in Figure 3. In Figure 3A, the equilibrium structures of three systems are shown, obtained using the equilibrium configurations of the oxazole-CO₂ complex and rotating N₂ around oxazole. However, in Figure 3B, the equilibrium structures of three other systems are displayed, obtained using the equilibrium configurations of the oxazole-N₂ complex and rotating CO₂ around oxazole. The structures in Figure 3A are identified by the symbol "InIm," where "In" and "Im" respectively represent the main complexation pathways (I1, I2, I3, I4, and I5) of CO₂ and N₂ with oxazole (Figure 1C), while in Figure 3B, they are identified by the symbol "ImIn". The binding energies in Table 6 are determined by combining the AVDZ basis set with MP2 correlation, which is an appropriate method for three-body systems. We opted for AVDZ over AVTZ due to the size of the systems,

Table 4. Harmonic fundamental frequencies (ω , in cm^{-1}) of N_2 , oxazole and the four equilibrium geometries of the oxazole- N_2 complexes calculated at the MP2/AVTZ level.

	Ω					
	Oxazole	N_2	I1A	I1B	I2A	I5
ω_1	a 3330		a 3330	a 3330	a 3329	a 3336
ω_2	3310		3314	3310	3316	3310
ω_3	3298		3298	3301	3298	3299
ω_4		σ_g 2187	2186	2185	2186	2186
ω_5	1545		1544	1545	1545	1546
ω_6	1507		1506	1507	1506	1508
ω_7	1355		1354	1354	1355	1356
ω_8	1271		1271	1271	1271	1273
ω_9	1185		1186	1186	1182	1186
ω_{10}	1141		1142	1140	1141	1141
ω_{11}	1109		1109	1110	1108	1113
ω_{12}	1085		1086	1086	1085	1085
ω_{13}	915		914	915	914	915
ω_{14}	904		905	904	904	905
ω_{15}	863		864	870	865	866
ω_{16}	826		834	827	833	827
ω_{17}	763		765	764	763	784
ω_{18}	664		666	665	665	665
ω_{19}	627		628	628	627	630
ω_{20}			84	82	77	58
ω_{21}			63	58	54	57
ω_{22}			46	46	42	49
ω_{23}			40	43	26	22
ω_{24}			21	20	13	9

Table 5. Binding energies of the oxazole complexes (E_b , kcal/mol).

Complex	E_{int} (MP2/AVTZ)	E_{int} (CCSD(T)F12/ AVTZ-F12)	E_{int} +BSSE (MP2/AVTZ)	E_{int} +ZPVE (MP2/AVTZ)	E_{int} +BSSE+ZPVE (MP2/AVTZ)
Oxazole-CO₂					
I1	-4.13	-3.96	-4.22	-3.62	-3.71
I2	-2.82	-2.64	-2.84	-2.43	-2.45
Oxazole-N₂					
I1A	-1.77	-1.19	-1.72	-1.38	-1.33
I1B	-1.76	-1.25	-1.71	-1.39	-1.37
I2A	-1.48	-1.01	-1.43	-1.16	-1.11
I5	-1.19	-0.78	-1.14	-0.85	-0.8

Figure 3. Three-body complexes composed by CO₂-oxazole-N₂. **A)** CO₂-oxazole + N₂ complexes, they are labeled using the symbol "InIm". "n" denotes the location of CO₂, and "m" refers to the position of N₂. **B)** N₂-oxazole + CO₂ complexes, they are labeled using the symbol "ImIn". "m" denotes the location of N₂ and "n" refers to the position of CO₂.

Figure 4. Optimized structures of Oxa-Au₆, Cu₆ and Zn₃O₃ and of CO₂/N₂-Oxa- Au₆, Cu₆ and Zn₃O₃ complexes at MP2/AVDZ/ LanL2DZ level of theory.

by the presence of the cluster. Consequently, in the structure II-Au₆ and II-Cu₆, the hydrogen bond between the oxygen O10 and H6 of the oxazole breaks, and a new hydrogen bond forms between O11 and H7 of the oxazole. The calculated MP2/AVDZ/ LanL2DZ Binding energies (BEs) of the CO₂/N₂-Oxa-Au₆, Cu₆ and Zn₃O₃ complexes are listed in Table 7. Our results show that metallic and metal oxide clusters favor the adsorption of CO₂ and N₂ gases. In hexametallc clusters, the adsorption energies (E_b) reach a maximum with the Cu₆ cluster, at -6.46 kcal/mol for CO₂ and -10.25 kcal/mol for N₂. However, the Au₆ and Zn₃O₃ clusters exhibit similar binding energy values: E_b(Au₆-I1) = -4.58 kcal/mol and E_b(Zn₃O₃-I1) = -4.56 kcal/mol for CO₂, and E_b(Au₆-I1) = -2.19 kcal/mol and E_b(Zn₃O₃-I1) = -2.22 kcal/mol for N₂. This is highly advantageous as it allows for the replacement of expensive gold clusters with more cost-effective materials such as Zn₃O₃.

Adsorption of CO₂ and N₂ in the metal and metal oxide surfaces (111)

The Molecular simulation (Monte Carlo) was conducted to examine the adsorption of CO₂ and N₂ on Au, Cu, and ZnO (111) surfaces. The choice of Au (111) and Cu (111) surfaces is motivated by the interest in the interaction of small molecules Au (111) surface. Furthermore, adsorption on noble metals (such as Cu, Ag, and Au) is considered a promising avenue for materials in future technologies and applications⁶⁷, however, the selection of ZnO aims to ensure high efficiency in the low-cost adsorption of pollutants. The investigation commenced with optimizing the geometries of the Oxa-CO₂ and Oxa-N₂ complexes using the COMPASS II force field in the Forcite Module. Subsequently, we constructed three-layer models for each surface (Au(111), Cu(111), and ZnO(111)). In the Adsorption Locator Module, we selected one of these surfaces and added the adsorbate, either Oxa-CO₂ or Oxa-N₂, before running the calculations. This process was repeated for all surfaces. The optimized geometries and their corresponding adsorption energies are depicted in the Figure 5. The calculations show spontaneous physisorption of CO₂ and N₂. Additionally, the ZnO surface is the most favorable for N₂ adsorption compared to CO₂, with an adsorption energy of -151.62 kcal/mol for N₂, while for CO₂, it reaches -148.01 kcal/mol. However, for the two other surfaces, Cu (111) and Au (111), the adsorption of CO₂ is more favorable than that of N₂, with respective adsorption energy values of -36.97 kcal/mol and -32.88 kcal/mol for Au, and -22.27 kcal/mol and -19.52 kcal/mol for Cu (111). Overall, our calculations demonstrate that the surfaces of gold (Au), copper (Cu), and zinc oxide (ZnO) are

capable of adsorbing N₂ and CO₂ from gas mixtures. Moreover, ZnO and Cu offer advantages in terms of adsorption capacity for both gases, without introducing additional cost-related issues.

Sorption isotherms

The adsorption isotherms of oxazole-CO₂ and oxazole-N₂ on Au (111), Cu (111), and ZnO (111) surfaces were calculated with the GCMC^{68,69} procedure implemented in the sorption module in BIOVIA Materials Studio. These simulations were carried out in the μ VT ensemble, where the chemical potential (μ), volume (V), and temperature (T) are held constant, allowing the number of gas molecules in the system to fluctuate naturally in response to the external reservoir. All simulations were performed at 298 K over a pressure range of 1000 to 10,000 kPa. The chemical potential corresponding to each pressure point was determined using the Peng–Robinson equation of state, which accounts for non-ideal gas behavior. The Metropolis algorithm was applied to sample system configurations through stochastic insertion, deletion, translation, and rotation of molecules, ensuring ensemble consistency. Long-range electrostatic interactions between the adsorbates and the surfaces were calculated using the Ewald summation method with an energy accuracy of 0.001 kcal/mol, while van der Waals interactions were modeled using the atom-based method with a cutoff distance of 12.5 Å. Each simulation consisted of 10,000 loading steps for system equilibration and 100,000 production steps to collect statistically meaningful adsorption data. This computational approach provides detailed insight into the pressure-dependent adsorption behavior of oxazole-functionalized gases on metallic

The GCMC adsorption isotherm is a key tool for evaluating and quantifying the gas adsorption capacity on the hosts. The adsorption isotherms of Oxazole-CO₂ and Oxazole-N₂ on Au (111), Cu (111), and ZnO (111) surfaces, presented in Figure 6, reveal that all three surfaces generally exhibit better adsorption performance for CO₂ compared to N₂.

For instance, at a pressure of 19 bars, the average loading of Oxazole-CO₂ is 57 on ZnO (111), and 69 on both Cu (111) and Au (111), whereas for Oxazole-N₂, the values are 56.6 for ZnO (111), 68.8 for Cu (111), and 65.9 for Au (111). When the pressure increases to 91 bars, the number of CO₂ molecules adsorbed reaches 65 on ZnO (111), and 79 on both Cu (111) and Au (111), while for Oxazole-N₂, the values reach 61, 74.5, and 76, respectively.

In the case of Oxazole-CO₂, the ZnO (111) surface appears to reach saturation adsorption equilibrium at a relatively high pressure, around 73 bars. In contrast, for Oxazole-N₂, equilibrium seems to be reached earlier, around 46 bars.

Given the trend of the adsorption isotherms, it is likely that the Au (111) and Cu (111) surfaces only reach adsorption equilibrium at around 55 bars for gold and 73 bars for copper in the case of Oxazole-CO₂. On the other hand, for Oxazole-N₂, adsorption continues to increase significantly with rising pressure. Therefore, the Cu surface, in particular,

Table 7. MP2/AVDZ/LanL2DZ binding energies of the CO₂/N₂-Oxa-Au₆, Cu₆ and Zn₃O₃ complexes (E_b, kcal/mol).

		Au ₆	Cu ₆	Zn ₃ O ₃
Complexes	I1	I1	I1	I1
Oxazole-CO ₂	-4.48	-4.58	-6.46	-4.56
Oxazole-N ₂	-1.77	-2.19	-10,25	-2.22

Figure 5. Optimized structures of Oxa- Au (111) /Cu (111) and ZnO (111) and of CO₂/N₂-Oxa@ Au (111)/ Cu (111) and ZnO (111) complexes, derived from the MC simulation.

Figure 6. Calculated Oxa-CO₂ and Oxa-N₂ adsorption isotherms at 298 K on Au (111), Cu (111), and ZnO (111) surfaces.

is expected to offer even greater adsorption capacity for both CO₂ and N₂ at higher pressures.

Conclusion

In summary, Our study demonstrates that oxazole has a significant adsorption capacity for both CO₂ and N₂, with a notably higher capacity for CO₂. The presence of a second gas does not affect oxazole's ability to capture both gases simultaneously, but it may enhance adsorption through the formation of hydrogen bonds among the three systems. The addition of clusters Au₆, Cu₆, and Zn₃O₃ to the most stable structures II of the Oxa-CO₂ complex and IIA of the Oxa-N₂ complex increases the adsorption capacity for both gases, with Cu₆ exhibiting the highest capacity compared to Au₆ and Zn₃O₃. Finally, the investigation of interactions between the most stable structures of the Oxa-CO₂ and Oxa-N₂ complexes with the three (111) surfaces of Au, Cu, and ZnO demonstrates that gold (Au), copper (Cu), and zinc oxide (ZnO) surfaces

are capable of adsorbing N₂ and CO₂ from gas mixtures. Moreover, Cu offer advantages in terms of adsorption capacity for both gases, without introducing additional cost-related issues.

Ethics and consent

Ethics and consent were not required.

Data availability statement

No data are associated with this article

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge the CTI of Universidad Autónoma de Chile and CSIC for computing facilities. And they express their gratitude to the grant FONDECYT 1241193 and the Researchers Supporting Project (RSPD2025R808) of King Saud University, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia.

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Open Peer Review

Current Peer Review Status:

Version 2

Reviewer Report 10 September 2025

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.21961.r58175>

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Dharamashi Rabari

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The research article explores molecular interactions through ab initio calculations. The findings suggest strong selectivity for CO₂ over N₂.

It can be accepted with following minor revisions.

- ○ Oxazole is first introduced without abbreviation; later, you use "Oxa." Please introduce the abbreviation at first mention, e.g., "oxazole (Oxa)" in introduction itself
- The statement "I recommend the open-source software Quantum ESPRESSO and CP2K" can be rephrased to a neutral tone
- Maintain uniform usage: e.g., "Oxazole-N₂" instead of switching between "Oxazole-N₂" and "oxazole-N₂." Similarly, use consistent formatting for Oxazole-CO₂.
- In Figure 1, the atom is marked as "H6," while in the text it is referred to as "Hydrogen 6." Please check.
- Figure 6: Specify the adsorption loading units used
- Revise "In summary,Our study" to "In summary, Our study" (spacing).
- ○ Oxazole is first introduced without abbreviation; later, you use "Oxa." Please introduce the abbreviation at first mention, e.g., "oxazole (Oxa)" in introduction itself
- The statement "I recommend the open-source software Quantum ESPRESSO and CP2K" can be rephrased to a neutral tone
- Maintain uniform usage: e.g., "Oxazole-N₂" instead of switching between "Oxazole-N₂" and "oxazole-N₂." Similarly, use consistent formatting for Oxazole-CO₂.
- In Figure 1, the atom is marked as "H6," while in the text it is referred to as "Hydrogen 6." Please check.
- Figure 6: Specify the adsorption loading units used
- Revise "In summary,Our study" to "In summary, Our study" (spacing).

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Yes

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Yes

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Yes

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Computational chemistry, Molecular Simulation, Deep Eutectic Solvents Applications

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard.

Reviewer Report 28 August 2025

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.21961.r57379>

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Driss benabdallah

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The manuscript is well written and easy to follow, with a clear structure and a good selection of recent references. The study uses a combination of *ab initio* MP2 calculations and Monte Carlo simulations for two-body, three-body, and surface adsorption systems. This approach is well

suiting to the topic and gives results of clear scientific interest, especially showing that oxazole binds more strongly to CO₂. The methods are described in enough detail to allow other researchers to repeat the work, although providing input files, Cartesian coordinates, and raw energies would make reproduction easier. No formal statistical analysis is needed, and the way the results are interpreted is reasonable. However, since there are no datasets linked to the article, sharing the source data would make the work more transparent and repeatable. The conclusions are supported by the structural, energetic, and adsorption isotherm results, and the suggested minor revisions are mainly to improve clarity, consistency, and small methodological points.

Main Points for Revision

1. Clarity and presentation

- Repetition error – Page 4, line ~16:
Replace 'to estimate the adsorption isotherms to estimate the adsorption isotherms' with: "...performed to estimate the adsorption isotherms of oxazole@CO₂ and oxazole@N₂ on Au(111), Cu(111), and ZnO(111) surfaces."
- Grammar – Page 4, line ~27:
"I recommend the open-source software Quantum ESPRESSO and CP2K" → replace 'software' by 'software packages'.
- Clarity – Page 5, lines 1–3:
Rewrite awkward sentence on structure optimization:
"The structures of oxazole, oxazole@N₂, and oxazole@CO₂ were optimized to obtain their lowest-energy configurations using the COMPASS II force field, as implemented in the Forcite Module."
- Paragraph restructuring – Page 6, lines 3–8:
Rewrite for clarity:
"This section examines the adsorption and activation of CO₂ and N₂ on small metal clusters (Au₆, Cu₆) and on the metal oxide cluster Zn₃O₃. Even-numbered clusters were chosen because they tend to be more stable and have larger HOMO–LUMO gaps, ensuring reliable structures during adsorption studies."
- Proofreading – Final check for grammar and typographic consistency.

2. Methodological details

- Computational details – Page 5, line ~20:
Clarify basis sets for metals and non-metals:
"...MP2 method with aug-cc-pVDZ for non-metals and LANL2DZ ECP for metals."
- Validation of MP2 – Suggest running a single-point CCSD(T)-F12 calculation on one representative complex (CO₂-Oxa or N₂-Oxa) to confirm MP2 accuracy.

3. Consistency and formatting

- Notation consistency – Throughout manuscript:
Use "CO₂-Oxa" instead of "Oxa@CO₂" for clarity and ensure consistent A/B labeling (CO₂ = A, N₂ = B).
- Figure/Table consistency –
 - Table 1: bold CO₂ as for Oxazole.
 - Table 3: bold N₂, check "ER" vs "Er".
 - Table 5: fix "Oxazole-0N₂" → "Oxazole-N₂".
 - Figures 2A/2B: clarify I1A, I2B, etc.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Yes

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Not applicable

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

No

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: My area of expertise is in non-reactive molecular dynamics, particularly ab initio calculations of potential energy surfaces for van der Waals systems, followed by the calculation of rotational transition cross-sections from molecular collisions, and the subsequent determination of collisional rate coefficients.

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Reviewer Report 27 August 2025

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.21961.r57251>

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Nguyen Thi Xuan Huynh

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There are no comments for the revised version.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Computational physics, Computational Physical Chemistry

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard.

Version 1

Reviewer Report 18 March 2025

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.20477.r50891>

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Nguyen Thi Xuan Huynh

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I have some additional suggestions as follows:

1. Check for spelling errors and wordiness in some places, and make sure it is concise and meaningful. For example, whether or not there is a comma "," or whether "the Figure ..." is used before the Figure, plural or singular, etc. There are many spelling mistakes in the manuscript, such MOF's (MOFs), labelling (labeling),...
2. Consistent use of kcal/mol energy units for Er (relative energies) in Tables 1 and 2, consistent with the data used in the text. Unify the use of the units in kcal/mol or kcal.mol⁻¹...
3. Calculations should be focused in the "Calculation details" section without needing to be explained separately in the results and discussion sections.
4. The authors should only give important information in the Conclusion section. For example, the authors can omit the first sentence about the method.
5. Please describe the Monte Carlo simulation method in more detail. This simulation method can quantify the gas adsorption capacity on the hosts. The authors should supplement their calculation results through adsorption isotherms.
6. The authors need to further elucidate the interactive nature of important adsorption systems through density of states or charge density differences.
7. Replace the figures due to blur and have to underline the captions, as shown in Figure 5.
8. Check your references in manuscript. Note that the superscript numerals are placed after quotation marks, commas, and periods.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Partly

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Yes

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Yes

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Computational physics, Computational Physical Chemistry

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 25 Apr 2025

samira dalbouha

We sincerely thank the reviewer for their valuable comments on our manuscript. These constructive remarks and suggestions have significantly contributed to the improvement of our work. In response to these comments, we have prepared a revised and enhanced version of the manuscript. (*The reviewer's comments are presented in italics.*) **Comment-1 :** *Check for spelling errors and wordiness in some places, and make sure it is concise and meaningful. For example, whether or not there is a comma "," or whether "the Figure ..." is used before the Figure, plural or singular, etc. There are many spelling mistakes in the manuscript, such MOF's (MOFs), labelling (labeling),...* **Reply-1 :** We have carefully reviewed the manuscript and addressed the spelling errors and wordiness issues as suggested. Proper punctuation has been ensured, singular/plural usage corrected, and references to figures standardized. Additionally, the specific spelling mistakes mentioned, such as MOF's (corrected to MOFs) and labelling (corrected to labeling), have been revised accordingly. **Comment-2 :** *Consistent use of kcal/mol energy units for Er (relative energies) in Tables 1 and 2, consistent with the data used in the text. Unify the use of the units in kcal/mol or kcal.mol⁻¹...* **Reply-2 :** We have taken your suggestion into account and have unified the use of energy units in Tables 1 and 2. The relative energy values (Er) are now consistently expressed in kcal/mol, in line with the data used in the text. **Comment-3 :** *Calculations should be focused in the "Calculation details" section without needing to be explained separately in the results and discussion sections.* **Reply-3 :** We have taken your suggestion into account and moved the calculation details to the "Calculation Details" section. **Comment-4 :** *The authors should only give important information in the Conclusion section. For example, the authors can omit the first sentence about the method.* **Reply-4 :** We have revised the Conclusion section to include only the essential information,

omitting the first sentence regarding the method, as suggested, to make it more concise and focused on the key results. **Comment-5** : *Please describe the Monte Carlo simulation method in more detail. This simulation method can quantify the gas adsorption capacity on the hosts. The authors should supplement their calculation results through adsorption isotherms.* **Rpply-5** : We have taken your suggestion into account and added a detailed description of the Monte Carlo simulation method in the article. Additionally, a new section titled "sorption Isotherms" has been included, along with Figure 6, which illustrates the adsorption isotherms. These additions complement our calculation results and allow for the quantification of the gas adsorption capacity on the hosts. **Comment-6** : *The authors need to further elucidate the interactive nature of important adsorption systems through density of states or charge density differences.* **Reply-6** : We thank the reviewer for this insightful comment. We would like to clarify that this article is part of a series of studies conducted within the framework of our research project on the adsorption of pollutant gases. A detailed investigation of the interactive nature of the adsorption systems, particularly through density of states (DOS) and charge density difference analyses, will be presented in a complementary article currently in preparation, which will specifically focus on the electronic aspects of the systems studied here. **Comment-7** : *Replace the figures due to blur and have to underline the captions, as shown in Figure 5.* **Reply-7** : We have taken your comment into account. All the blurred figures have been replaced with higher-quality versions, specifically Figures 1, 2, 3A, 3B, and 5. **Comment-8** : *Check your references in manuscript. Note that the superscript numerals are placed after quotation marks, commas, and periods.* **Reply-8** : We have taken your comment into account and revised the manuscript accordingly. The superscript reference numerals have been repositioned to appear after quotation marks, commas, and periods, as required.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Comments on this article

Version 2

Reviewer Response 05 Aug 2025

Xuan Huynh Nguyen

There are no comments for this version. I agree with the revised version.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.
